

collected them on the roadside, carefully removed the soil sticking to the roots, and later air-dried it. The soil was a red sandy loam. On weighing the air-dried soil, we noted that an average of 0.7 kg

of dry soil was removed for each hill uprooted.

At a 20- × 10-cm spacing the plant population in our plots is 500,000 hills/ha. If a modest 10% of the hills are removed

as rogues, the estimated soil losses would be 35 t/ha in a single crop season. To avoid this staggering loss of topsoil, we suggest that plants be rogued by cutting them close to the base. ■

Introduction of puddling, an Asian technique, in rice production in Colombia

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Rice production in Colombia is characterized by high yields and high production costs. In the same period

that yields increased by 77% (the national average for irrigated rice is 5.5 t/ha), production costs increased by 670%, (up to about US\$1,200/ha). Those trends make further yield increases difficult.

Therefore the National Rice Growers Federation (FEDEARROZ) is investigating the introduction of puddling techniques from Asia into Colombian

rice fields. In 1979 an intensive program, conducted to provide technical assistance to farmers, included help with plot design, mechanization, and crop management. About 5,000 ha are now puddled.

Puddling has increased the average yield in that area by about 7% and lowered production costs by about 20%. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Traditional cultural practices in rainfed wetland rice cultivation in Moyna Basin, Midnapore, West Bengal, India

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Little is known about traditional cultivation practices for the traditional tall indicas cultivated in deepwater areas. In the 1977 wet season the problems and behavior of the varieties were surveyed in the 4,000-ha Moyna Bheel basin area in Midnapore District, West Bengal. A water regime of about 1.5–2 m is usually reached in about 50% of the basin area during the peak precipitation period; the water remains stagnant for 3–4 months. The average annual precipitation is about 1,800 mm, most of which falls from June to October. Two factors govern successful rice cultivation in such lands; proper land preparation at sowing, and proper stand establishment before inundation of the rice plants.

The land in the basin area can be classified into three main water depth categories: 1.0 m, 1–1.5 m, and more than 1.5 m.

The soil in the 1.0-m depth category remains moist until March. After harvest, the stubble (91–122 cm long) is left to

dry. The dry stubble is burned to destroy hibernating insects and wild rice seeds, and to facilitate tillage in the black peat soil. The presoaked seeds are then sown at 125 kg/ha and the land is plowed once and then laddered. Pregerminated seeds are then sown again at the same rate; the land is plowed again and laddered 10–12 times to level and compact the soil. Depending on soil condition, the field is further laddered until the topsoil consists of fine particles.

Land in the 1- to 1.5-m category is plowed twice and then kept fallow for 10–15 days. If there is no rain, dry seeds are sown in dry soil. The field is laddered after the rains come and germination begins. If soil moisture conditions permit, laddering is done three or four times.

Where water depth exceeds 1.5 m, dry seeds are generally sown after the harvest of the dry season crop; the land is then alternatively plowed and laddered. Dry or germinated seeds are generally broadcast, depending on the soil moisture content.

For fertilizer, Moyna Basin farmers apply bonemeal at 125 kg/ha, and decomposed farmyard manure and ash at 2.5 t/ha immediately after sowing. Progressive basin area farmers report that a rainless period of 1–1.5 months is

desirable for proper soil condition and minimum weed growth. Weeding is generally practiced when water accumulates 1.5–2 months after sowing.

A good stand is usually established about 2 months after sowing, before much water has accumulated. When the crop has attained a good stand, the plants can withstand submergence and waterlogging. Average yields of 3 t/ha are common.

The following traditional varieties are predominant in the basin:

For areas where water depth is about 1.0 m: Amol, Kamod, Gaira, Bhuto, Bakui.

For areas where water reaches 1.5 m and deeper: Pankalas green, Pankalas pigmented, Tangra, Bauskata.

In the basin where water reaches 1.5 m or deeper, rice plants were uprooted and their tillering patterns and nodal rooting were studied. Tillering was from the base only and nodal roots were present. The traditional varieties can yield about 3 t/ha, provided fields are inundated about 2 months after sowing. In the past, when water in such areas had currents, varieties with nodal tillers were grown. But since channels and bunds for flood prevention had been installed, farmers have preferred basal tillering rices that yield better and are harvested more easily. ■